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JERRY PHILIP MARTIN, MN, MAN

Instructor I

JH Cerilles State University

jerryphilip.martin@jhsc.edu.ph

"OUR HOME YOU LEFT BEHIND"

You used to fill the doorway wide,
A shadow tall at eventide,
Your gleefulness warmed my room,
Your safety voice is my shield for home.

But seasons shift, and hearts can stray,
And promises can fade away.
One morning came without goodbye,
Just heavy breath and questions why?

Your suits are gone, a vacant chair.
Your scent is still around in the air.
The clock kept ticking, unaware.
A father's love was it no longer there?

I heard you built another home,
With different hands for you to hold.
A different child upon his knee.
A life rewritten so quietly.

Yet in this home, his echoes stay,
In the report cards signed yesterday,
My birthday cakes with candles bright,
My whispered prayers at night.

A son still waits in silent grace,
For footsteps on our porch to trace.
Not anger now, but aching plea:
"Papa, have you forgotten about me?"

But strength grew where you left a scar,
Like stubborn weeds through pavement's tar.
A mother's arms became my wall,
A fortress standing through it all.

And though your new family is on the way,
The sun will always rise every day,
For love is more than blood alone.
It's what remains when one has gone?

